

THE PECULIARITIES OF USING VISUAL MATERIALS FOR TEACHING ENGLISH

Anarkulova Zubayda Fayzullo qizi

O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillar universitet o'qituvchisi

Aminboyeva Muxlisa

2-year student of UzSWLU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042712>

Abstract: In this article we revealed the advantages of utilizing visual materials (e.g., pictures, flash cards, cartoons, and films) as an innovative method of easing difficulties which learners may undergo in the process of gaining language knowledge and inspire them to learn this target language with enthusiasm.

Key words: Visual materials, teacher method, easiness, colorful, memorable

Аннотация: В этой статье мы раскрыли преимущества использования визуальных материалов (например, изображений, карточки, мультфильмов и фильмов) в качестве инновационного метода облегчения трудностей, с которыми учащиеся могут столкнуться в процессе получения языковых знаний, и вдохновили их на изучение этого. целевой язык с энтузиазмом.

Ключевые слова: визуальные материалы, метод учителя, легкость, красочность, запоминаемость

Education is a vital process for all human beings, without it no one can reach a good life. Important elements of education are considered to be teaching and learning. Teachers may use varieties of interesting strategies to conduct their lessons in order to attract students to the lesson. Now, there is a significant difference between today's teaching process and in the past. Modern teachers are using technologies such as projectors, computers, video players, cartoons for children and films rather than depending on a single text book.

According to L.Cuban's research we have found out that 83% of knowledge is obtained by sight while hearing and touching make up 11% and 1.5% respectively [1,4].

So, it means that technical devices have greater impact on teaching. Visual aids are the devices that help the teacher to clarify, and organize understandings and support him to make learning more active, motivated.

From our experience we can say that every individual has the tendency to forget. Using appropriate visual materials or aids can help to maintain more knowledge constantly. If students see and hear simultaneously they can improve their imagination clearly. Visual aids provide full examples for conceptual thinking. Moreover, they may enhance the range of vocabulary and give direct experience to the learners.

Learning can be strengthened with different teaching or learning resources and help the teachers to explain the topic easily. In 2005 Singh clarified that any device which by sight and sound increases the individuals' practice, outside that attained through reading labeled as an audio visual aids. Visual aids are those instructional devices which are used in the classroom to encourage learning and make it easier and motivating. The material like models, charts, film strip, projectors, radio, television, maps etc called instructional aids [3,7].

According to Rather's view, visual aids are regarded as effective tools that "invest the past with an air of reality." They distribute the learners with true knowledge, which detention their devotion and help in the understanding of the ancient marvels. They demand to the mind

through the visual auditory senses. When we use visual aids as teaching aid, it is one of the aspects which root participation of students in the lesson because when students look at visual model or aid, it is measured as a kind of contribution. Also the uses of visual aids encourage the body movement and it may strengthen the control [2,11].

There is famous universal proverb which can be found in any nations: “One sighted is better than, a hundred words” it is fact that we learn through our intellects. The teaching career is full of endless opportunities to enrich the academic survives of students, while some ideas and educational goals will be easy for students to hold, other will need you to think productively to ensure that important learning aims are met. With the help of visual materials students can obtain deep knowledge. The teacher may extend his or her work with them and this helps to color white and black text books. Singh mentioned the saying of a well known teacher, Comenius: The foundation of all learning consists in representing clearly to the senses and sensible objects so they can be appreciated easily [3].

Visual aids or materials are designated materials that may be locally made or commercially produced. They come in form of, for illustration, wall charts, posters, exemplified pictures, symbolic materials and other two dimensional items. There are also audio visual aids. These are can be called as teaching machines like television, computers, and all kinds of projectors with sound attributes .Television or computer programs supply another advantageous learning resource. Films, likewise, are a general teaching/learning resource. It can be a goal for all teachers if the students are able to retain as much knowledge of the topic as possible, particularly the main points.To draw the conclusion, we can incline that visual aids or materials are nothing short of beneficial support in teaching, because they may give motivation, make the topic understandable; on the other hand they may help to direct experience. We can use visual aids such as pictures, graphic organizers, charts, video and computers can help students easily understand and realize the main points they have learnt at the lesson. Every visual aid, students have different responses, and expressions because of their different educational and cultural background. Realia is one of the best effective visual aid in the ESL classroom. Realia means real-life, authentic items. For instance, when I was teaching a lesson about booking a hotel room, students became much more engaged when I gave them at an actual hotel brochure to look at. I used the brochure to introduce new language items, and even as the basis for a role play.

I highly recommend taking some time to build a realia collection for your ESL classes. Take a walk around town or go online to gather some essential realia. So visual materials are effective tools teachers can use in the classroom to enhance students’ interest, comprehension, and retention of information and concepts. Visual materials can help teachers establish, explain, connect, and associate ideas and concepts to make the process of learning more interesting, enjoyable, and effective. Here are given benefits of visual materials provide for teaching and learning include:

- Helping inspire students to study more effectively
- Helping students retain information for a longer period of time
- Providing an example to think about concepts
- Increasing the student’s vocabulary
- Helping students gain a proper view of topics and concepts
- Providing hands on experience for students

- Creating an atmosphere of interest
Making the process of teaching easier for teachers

References:

1. Larry Cuban .Oversold and overused, London ,2001
2. A.Rather. Essentials instructional technology, published by Darya Gaj, 2004.
3. Y Singh. Instructional technology in education, published by Darya Gaj, New Delhi
4. www.britishcouncil.org .com

